

KEY INFORMANT INTERVIEW BARANGAY OFFICIAL

Instructions

- This questionnaire must be completed with information provided by the **captain of the considered Barangay**. If the Barangay captain is not present, ask for another representative of the Barangay, e.g., secretary who can answer the questionnaire.
- Make sure that you explain the informed consent model, and how study results are reported to LGUs.
- No question will remain unanswered without justification.
- Do not read out questions loudly and instead try to have a conversation with the respondent.

Enumerator introduction

*“Good morning/ afternoon/ Sir/ Madam, My name is (name of enumerator), a field enumerator involved in the **research project** "CITIZEN-SDSS". The goal of the research project is to support the development of long-term environmental management pathways to sustain local livelihoods in your Barangay and surrounding areas.*

*We are currently in the first phase of **the research project**. We are conducting this survey to understand the Barangay household’s current livelihood conditions, their perceptions on land quality and ecosystem services. We are further interested to learn how the pandemic influenced the use of natural resources. The information of this survey will be used to provide recommendations to LGUs for improving the quality of local interventions and programmes based on science and research. The main purpose is to support local livelihoods and nature conversation.*

*In this regard, I (we) would **like to conduct an expert interview with you**. Please, be assured any information of this interview will be treated with privacy, and the information of the interview is used for research purposes only.”*

Informed consent

Your participation in this survey is completely voluntary. If you do not want to participate or answer some questions, please inform us immediately. If you feel uncomfortable at some point and do not want to continue, please inform the enumerator. If a particular question is not clear or if you want any further explanation, please feel free to ask.

Are willing to conduct this survey?

Yes=1, No=0	
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If the answer is no, say thank you and try to identify another Barangay official for a KII.

If the answer is yes, let the respondent sign below, plus providing date, name and location.

Date	Location	Name of respondent	Signature

A General information

A1. Interview

1. Name of enumerator:

1.1 First name	1.2 Middle Name	1.3 Last name
2. Date of interview: (mm/dd/yyyy)	3. Time started (hh:mm):	4. Time ended (hh:mm):

A2. Respondent

2. Name of Barangay official and designation/ tasks:

2.1 First name	2.2 Middle Name	2.3 Last name
2.4 Designation/ Tasks		
2.5 Gender (1= male, 2= female, 3= prefer not to mention)		
2.5 Cellphone number		
2.6 Messenger account/ ID		

In case no cellphone/ messenger ID available, ask to get contact information from other Barangay official and write down name.

2.7.1 Name:	2.7.2 Phone number:
	2.7.3 Messenger ID:

A3. Barangay

3. Name of Barangay and Municipality

3.1 Barangay:	3.2 Municipality:

4. How many households and inhabitants does the village have?

4.1 Households	4.2 Inhabitants

5. Estimate the number of **households whose main occupation** is.....? In case, key informant cannot give an answer in household numbers, ask for an estimation in % and note down the unit.

• Own farming (including livestock farming or animal husbandry)	
• Agricultural laborer (including livestock farming or animal husbandry)	
• Wage labourer outside agriculture	
• Small business outside agriculture	
• Government employee	

6. Describe the **main access road** to the Barangay:

Code list road access (6): 1=Paved Road, 2=one single lane, 3=two lane road, 4=Seasonal Road, 5=Footpath, 6=Others, specify, 99=no answer

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7. What is the **main source of drinking and irrigation water** in the Barangay?

7.1 Specify source	7.2 Drinking water (1=yes, 0=no)	7.3 Irrigation water (1=yes, 0=no)
1:		
2:		
3:		

8. Estimate **distance from Barangay hall** to Mayor's office of **Municipality/ City** (using straight line)?

Kilometers	
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B. Wages and Prices

9. What was the **typical daily wage rate for unskilled agricultural/ casual** adult male and female labour **during the past 12 months?** (**Note:** Adult = 18 years or older)

9.1 Wage type	9.2 Male adult (PHP per day)	9.3 Female adult (PHP per day)
Agricultural wage		
Non farm wage		

10. What was the **average price per kg** for the following crops/ products during the past 12 months?

ID	Crop / Product	Average sale price (no answer= -99)
1	Rice unmilled	
2	Rice milled	
3	Maize comb	
4	Maize grain	
5	Coconut young (Buko)	
6	Coconut brown (mature)	
7	Coconut dehusked	
8	Coconut lumber (per m ²)	
9	Copra	
10	Cocoa	
11	Abaca	
12	Firewood (per kg)	
13	Fiewood Coconut residues (per kg)	
14	Charcoal from wood	
15	Charcoal from coconut husks	

C. Land degradation

11. What type of land degradation can be **observed in your Barangay?** (Multiple ticks allowed).
If no, (enter=99) in grey box.

Code list degradation level (11):

99=no answer, 1=Very low, 2=Low, 3=Moderate, 4=High, 5=Very high

ID	Observed land degradation	11.1	11.2
		Tick (yes=1, no=0)	Degradation level
1	Decline of crop production		
2	Increase in weed infestations		
3	Soil erosion		
4	Soil compaction by use of heavy machinery		
5	Soil pollution by chemicals		
6	Overuse of pesticides and herbicides		
7	Decline of soil fertility		
8	Deforestation		
9	Decrease in availability of timber and wood products		
10	Decrease in availability of NTFPs		
11	Biodiversity loss: animal species		
12	Biodiversity loss: plant species		
13	Decrease availability of irrigation water		
14	Decrease availability of drinking water		
15	Decrease of water quality		
16	Decrease in groundwater level		
90	Other known land degradation, specify:		

Note: NTFPs - e.g., edible plants, animals, medicinal plants

12. What are the main reasons of the observed land degradation? **(Multiple answers allowed).**
Name up to 3 per land degradation reason.

If no (enter=99) in grey box, proceed to next question.

Code list land degradation reasons (12)

Climate change

- 1 Increasing risk of typhoons
- 2 Increasing risk of flooding
- 3 Increasing risk of heat spells
- 4 Increasing risk of droughts
- 5 Increasing risk of forest fires
- 90 Others specify

Natural disasters

- 10 Typhoons
- 11 Flooding
- 12 Droughts
- 13 Pest outbreaks
- 14 Weed infestation
- 90 Others specify

Agricultural practices

- 20 Overuse of fertilizers
- 21 Overuse of pesticides
- 22 Ploughing
- 23 No soil erosion protection
- 24 Overgrazing
- 25 Kaingin
- 90 Others specify

Other reasons

- 30 Uncontrolled local garbage management
- 31 Construction of irrigation channels
- 32 Settlement expansion
- 33 Road construction
- 34 Mismatch between government intervention / programme and local needs to mitigate land degradation
- 35 Domestic in-migration
- 36 Natural conditions of environment: shallow or acidic soils
- 37 Natural conditions of environment: topography or inclination
- 90 Others specify

ID	Land degradation reasons (name the 3 most important ones)	(Code list)
CC_1	Climate change	
CC_2	Climate change	
CC_3	Climate change	
ND_1	Natural disasters	
ND_2	Natural disasters	
ND_3	Natural disasters	
PAP_1	Poor agricultural practices	
PAP_2	Poor agricultural practices	
PAP_3	Poor agricultural practices	
OTH_1	Other reasons	
OTH_2	Other reasons	
OTH_3	Other reasons	

C. Risks and Disasters

13. Has the Barangay faced any of the following crises or disasters **during the past 12 months?**

Code list risks or disasters: 0= no, 1= yes, moderate crises, 2= yes, severe crises

ID	Risks or disasters	Code list
1	Typhoons	
2	Floodings	
3	Landslides	
4	Drought	
5	Wild fires in forest areas	
6	Wild fires in grasland areas	
7	Wild fires in agricultural / plantation areas	
8	Widespread crop pest/ disease	
9	Widespread animal disease	
10	Strong decrease of prices for agricultural/ plantation outputs	
11	Strong increase of prices for agricultural/ plantation inputs	
12	Conflicts on natural resources (e.g., theft, timber poaching)	
13	Bridge/ road was destroyed/ washed away	
14	Land tenure/ titling conflicts within village	
15	High level of in-migration	
90	Others, specify	

D. Tenurial instruments and environmental management interventions

14. Which tenurial instruments can be found in this barangay?

Code list tenurial instrument (15)

- | | | | | | |
|---|---------|---|-------|----|------------------------|
| 1 | CBFMA | 5 | FLGMA | 9 | Tree farm lease |
| 2 | PACBRMA | 6 | FLMA | 10 | MOA with farmers (NGP) |
| 3 | ISF | 7 | SIFMA | 11 | Forest without tenure |
| 4 | CSC | 8 | IFMA | 12 | CLOA |
| | | | | 90 | Other, specify |
| | | | | 99 | No answer |

Tenurial instruments found in the barangay:
(Separate codes with “,”)

15. What **environmental management interventions or measures** are practised in this Barangay to avoid or minimise land degradation? (**Multiple answer allowed**).

If no (enter=99) in grey box.

ID	Mitigation measures land degradation	Tick (yes=1, no=0)
1	Crop rotation	
2	Cover cropping	
3	Intercropping	
4	Multi-cropping	
5	Use of organic fertilizers	
6	Terracing	
7	Contour plowing	
8	Timber tree planting	
9	Fruit tree planting	
10	Other kind of tree planting	
11	Rotational and controlled grazing	
12	Stop timber poaching from forests areas	
13	Stop extracting firewood from forest areas	
14	Stop extracting NTFPs from forest areas	
90	Others (specify)	

16. Are any of these interventions or measures related to government programmes or projects, e.g., by DENR, DA or NIA? If yes, name the programmes/ project, its duration and objective.

17.1 Name of Programme/ Project	17.2 Duration	17.3 Objective

E. CHECK LIST ENUMERATOR

- **THANK** the key informant again for his/ her time and willingness for the KII.
- Inform the key informant that we will use the provided information for our research analysis and this requires about 12 months to complete. Once we are done, we will report back our results to LGU representatives, and will invite selected members of the Barangay for a feedback workshop.
- Confirm again that names of key informant will be **NOT disclosed** to anyone else.
- Did the key informant **SIGN the consent** form already?
- Do you have the full name and **contact details** of the respondent: **phone number** and **messenger ID**? (In case of no phone number or messenger ID, get from another Barangay official)